

Table S1. Loci incorrectly named in the genome browser v. 5.1.9 (an extended version of Table 3)

Name [†]	Actual locus ID (publication)	Publication	Misnamed locus ID (v. 5.1.9)	Correct name and publication for a misnamed locus
MtCbf4	MtrunA17_Chr1g0203861	Zhang et al., 2016b	MtrunA17_Chr1g0195851	MtNF-YB6 (Baudin et al., 2015)
MtChOMT1 [‡]	MtrunA17_Chr1g0200491	Wu et al., 2024	MtrunA17_Chr3g0085211, MtrunA17_Chr7g0218131	MtOMT2 (Wu et al., 2024), MtChOMT3 (Wu et al., 2024)
MtGA20ox1	MtrunA17_Chr1g0204181	Li et al., 2021b	MtrunA17_Chr6g0474391	MtGA20ox7 (Li et al., 2021b)
MtHDT3	MtrunA17_Chr7g0265761	Li et al., 2021a	MtrunA17_Chr4g0027181	MtHDT1 (Li et al., 2021a)
MtMYC2	MtrunA17_Chr8g0366751	Guo et al., 2024	MtrunA17_Chr5g0411341	MtBHLH2 (Deng et al., 2019)
MtPRP1 [‡]	MtrunA17_Chr4g0013391	Erickson et al., 2020	MtrunA17_Chr4g0013371, MtrunA17_Chr4g0013401	MtPRP2 (Erickson et al., 2020), MtPRP3 (Erickson et al., 2020)
MtPRR7	MtrunA17_Chr1g0181811	Wang et al., 2023g	MtrunA17_Chr8g0345901	MtPRR9b (Wang et al., 2023g)
MtRac1	MtrunA17_Chr6g0486041	Wang et al., 2021d	MtrunA17_Chr4g0046211	MtROP7a (Wang et al., 2021d)
MtROP9	MtrunA17_Chr5g0405791	Kiirika et al., 2012	MtrunA17_Chr6g0486041	MtRac1 (Wang et al., 2021d)
MtSCR	MtrunA17_Chr7g0245601	Dong et al., 2021	MtrunA17_Chr5g0396491	MtSCL3 (Seemann et al., 2022)
MtSLB1	MtrunA17_Chr5g0447381	Yin et al., 2020; Zhou et al., 2021	MtrunA17_Chr5g0447371	NA

[†]The table lists correct names and corresponding locus identifiers. These names were incorrectly assigned to other loci in the genome browser v. 5.1.9, which are shown in column 4.

[‡]Names MtChOMT1 and MtPRP1 were misassigned to two genes each in the genome browser v. 5.1.9.

References in this table have letter codes (a, b, c, etc.) according to Data S7, which may be different from the letter codes in the main text.